

Effect of green manure (GM) and Fe application on the Fe held by organic matter in redried submerged soils

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We investigated the effect of GM and Fe application on the Fe held by the organic matter in redried soils that varied in CaCO₃ content. The pot culture experiment was conducted on highly calcareous (pH 8.7, 0.56% organic C, 4.7% CaCO₃, and Fe held by organic matter at 25.3 mg/kg) and slightly calcareous (pH 8.5, 0.17% organic C, 0.25% CaCO₃, and Fe held by organic matter at 62.2 mg/kg) soils (Aeric Fluvaquent). pH was measured in a 1:2 soil:water suspension.

Two levels of dry green manure (0 and 1%) from *Sesbania aculeata* (total Fe content 307 mg/kg) and 4 Fe levels (0, 15, 30, and 60 mg/kg) from FeSO₄·7H₂O were used. Soils were submerged 85 and 145 d, then dried 30 d.

To determine Fe held by organic matter, dried soil was allowed to react overnight with 30% H₂O₂ (1:1 soil H₂O₂ ratio). The soil tubes were immersed in a beaker containing water maintained at 75°C + 2°C for completion of the reaction. Fe was

extracted with DTPA (1:4 soil DTPA ratio). To calculate Fe held by organic matter, a blank reading (without H₂O₂) was abstracted.

Submerging soil for 85 d increased the Fe held by organic matter from 25.3 to 28.9 mg/kg for highly calcareous soil and from 62.2 to 79.8 mg/kg for slightly calcareous soils (see table). Fe content further increased to 30.2 and 90.0 mg/kg after 145 d of submergence. The effect of submergence was more pronounced on slightly calcareous soil.

GM increased organic bound Fe significantly in both soils in both submergence periods. The effect was higher at 85 d in slightly calcareous soil; in highly calcareous soil, the effect was almost the same for both submergence intervals.

Adding Fe increased organic bound Fe significantly in both soils at both submergence intervals.

The interaction between GM and added Fe was significant only at 85 d of submergence in both the soils. □

Effect of GM and Fe application on Fe held by organic matter in soils redried after being submerged. Ludhiana, Punjab, India.

Fe applied (mg/kg)	Fe held by organic matter (mg/kg)					
	Submerged 85 d			Submerged 145 d		
	No GM	GM	Mean	No GM	GM	Mean
	Highly calcareous soil					
0	28.9	35.1	32.0	30.2	36.3	33.2
15	30.9	37.0	33.9	31.8	37.3	34.5
30	33.3	37.9	35.6	33.4	39.1	36.3
60	35.8	39.7	37.7	34.2	41.7	37.9
Mean	32.2	37.4		32.4	38.6	
	Slightly calcareous soil					
0	79.8	91.7	85.8	90.0	91.8	90.9
15	83.0	97.0	90.0	92.9	94.2	93.5
30	85.2	101.8	93.5	94.5	96.8	97.7
60	88.6	103.6	96.1	97.1	98.8	97.9
Mean	84.2	98.5		93.6	95.4	
CD (0.05)Fe		GM	Fe × GM	Fe	GM	Fe × GM
Calcareous	0.5	0.4	0.7	1.0	0.7	ns
Noncalcareous	0.6	0.5	0.9	0.8	0.5	ns

Estimating azolla cover

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Quantitative estimates of azolla cover during multiplication are important in assessing its agronomic applications and weed-suppressing properties. The faster covering occurs, the greater its weed suppression efficiency. When studying large areas in farmers' fields, it is useful to have a simple but precise method that is faster than the usual fresh and dry weight measurement.

A new scoring method, based on the Braun Blanquet Cover-Abundance

Scale, is proposed. The Braun Blanquet method is used by ecologists all over the world. In the table, the new scale is compared to the IRRI

scale used in azolla INSFFER trials.

The new scale is more precise: it gives, within the significant range of cover, lower and upper limits. Errors

Two scoring methods for estimating azolla cover.

IRRI method	Modified Braun Blanquet method
0 = no azolla	r = rare with small cover
2 = 25% azolla cover	+ = few, with small cover
4 = 50% azolla cover	1 = numerous but less than 1/20 cover (<5%)
6 = 75% azolla cover	2 = cover between 1/20 and 1/4 (6-25%)
8 = 100% azolla cover	3 = cover between 1/4 and 1/2 (26-50%)
10 = 100% azolla cover with overlapping growth	4 = cover between 1/2 and 3/4 (51-75%)
	5 = cover more than 3/4 (>75%)
	6 = cover more than 3/4 (>75%) with overlapping growth of azolla